

Crystal Structure of Dimeric Tetraquapyridinioacetateytterbium(III) Perchlorate $[\text{Yb}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NCH}_2\text{CO}_2)_2 \cdot 4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]_2 \cdot (\text{ClO}_4)_6$

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The title complex dimeric tetraquapyridinioacetateytterbium perchlorate ($[\text{Yb}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NCH}_2\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]_2 \cdot (\text{ClO}_4)_6$) has been prepared by reacting ytterbium perchlorate with pyridine betaine (pyridinioacetate) in warm water and its X-ray crystal structure has been determined. The ytterbium(III) ion is surrounded by four carboxylato O atoms and four aqua-ligands in an eight-coordinate approximate dodecahedral arrangement. The average Yb-O (aqua), Yb-O (carboxylato) bond distances are 2.366(3) and 2.283(3) Å respectively.

Rare earth elements are now used extensively in agriculture, medicine and biochemical research. Therefore, it is important to understand their biological effects. The structures and properties of some rare earth amino acid coordination compounds have been investigated¹.

Betaine and its derivatives have structures analogous to the amino acids. They can take zwitterionic form containing positive charged quaternary ammonium. In this paper, the structure of an dimeric tetraquapyridinioacetateytterbium perchlorate ($[\text{Yb}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NCH}_2\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]_2 \cdot (\text{ClO}_4)_6$) is reported.

Results and Discussion

The crystal structure consists of discrete dinuclear $[\text{Yb}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NCH}_2\text{CO}_2)_2 \cdot 4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]_2^{3+}$ cations and $(\text{ClO}_4)^-$ anions. Each aqua-ligand in the complex forms donor hydrogen bonds with the lattice water molecules, the

perchlorate anions are not involved in hydrogen bonding. The molecular structure and the molecular packing arrangement in the unit cell of the complex are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively. Crystal data are presented in Table 1.

TABLE I—CRYSTAL DATA

Chemical formula	$\text{Yb}_2\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_4\text{O}_{40}\text{Cl}_6$	Crystal system	Triclinic
Crystal size	$0.40 \times 0.50 \times 0.52$	Mr	1635.31
Space group	$P\bar{1}$	T(K)	293
$a(\text{Å})$	9.045(1)	$\alpha(^{\circ})$	97.83(2)
$b(\text{Å})$	11.249(2)	$\beta(^{\circ})$	105.16(1)
$c(\text{Å})$	15.157(2)	$\gamma(^{\circ})$	112.30(1)
Z	1	$V(\text{Å}^3)$	1328.5(4)
$D_c(\text{g cm}^{-3})$	2.03	$D_o(\text{g cm}^{-3})$	2.05
$\mu(\text{cm}^{-1})$	146.3	$F(000)$	805.86
Scan mode	$\theta/2\theta$	Scan range($^{\circ}$)	$1 < \theta < 70$
$\lambda(\text{Å})(\text{MoK}\alpha)$	0.71073	Absorption coefficient	39.02
Data collection :			
Transition factors	0.345–0.431	Collection range	$h \pm k \pm l$
S	1.541	R_{int}	0.0124
R	0.0270	$2\theta_{\text{max}}$	48
R^w	0.0261	Standard variation	1.5%
Measured reflection	4498	No. of variable	362
Observed reflection	4056		
Weighting scheme	$w = 1$		

Fig. 1. Molecular structure of the complex; H atoms have been omitted for clarity.

The Yb^{3+} center in the dinuclear cation, which is located at an inversion centre, is bridged by four pyBET ligands. Each metal atom forms four short Yb-O (carboxylato) bonds [Yb-O(1) = 2.256(3), Yb-O(2a) = 2.262(3), Yb-O(3a) = 2.291(4), Yb-O(4) = 2.235(4) Å, average bond distance = 2.283(3) Å] and four Yb-O (aqua) bond [Yb-O(5) = 2.398(4), Yb-O(6) = 2.337(3), Yb-O(7) = 2.337(3), Yb-O(8) = 2.394(4) Å, average bond distance = 2.336(3) Å] in an approximate D_{2d} dodecahedron coordination geometry. The non-bonded Yb(a)···Yb separation is 4.410(2) Å. Selected bond distances and angles for the $[\text{Yb}(\text{pyBET})_2 \cdot 4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]_2^{3+}$ cation are shown in Table 2 and atomic coordinates and isotropic thermal parameters in Table 3.

TABLE 2—SELECTED BOND DISTANCES (Å) AND ANGLES (°)

Yb-O(1)	2.256(3)	Yb(a)-O(2)	2.262(3)
Yb-O(4)	2.325(4)	Yb(a)-O(3)	2.291(4)
Yb-O(5)	2.398(4)	C(1)-O(1)	1.243(7)
Yb-O(6)	2.337(3)	C(1)-O(2)	1.248(6)
Yb-O(7)	2.337(3)	C(1)-C(2)	1.528(5)
Yb-O(8)	2.394(4)	C(5)-C(6)	1.344(14)
Yb-O(2a)	2.262(3)	C(5)-C(4)	1.361(13)
Yb-O(3a)	2.291(4)	C(3)-C(4)	1.408(13)
N(1)-C(2)	1.469(7)	C(6)-C(7)	1.361(10)
N(1)-C(3)	1.335(9)	C(8)-O(3)	1.235(7)
N(1)-C(7)	1.338(8)	C(8)-O(4)	1.253(6)
O(1)-Yb-O(4)	74.5(1)	O(5)-Yb-O(2a)	72.1(1)
O(1)-Yb-O(5)	139.1(1)	O(5)-Yb-O(3a)	139.7(1)
O(1)-Yb-O(6)	81.3(1)	O(6)-Yb-O(7)	94.7(1)
O(1)-Yb-O(7)	141.7(1)	O(6)-Yb-O(8)	70.8(1)
O(1)-Yb-O(2a)	121.6(1)	O(8)-Yb-O(2a)	141.4(1)
O(1)-Yb-O(3a)	78.2(1)	O(6)-Yb-O(3a)	143.6(1)
O(1)-Yb-O(8)	71.8(1)	O(7)-Yb-O(8)	71.0(1)
O(4)-Yb-O(5)	70.9(1)	O(7)-Yb-O(2a)	84.1(1)
O(4)-Yb-O(6)	79.7(1)	O(7)-Yb-O(3a)	83.4(1)
O(4)-Yb-O(7)	142.6(1)	O(8)-Yb-O(2a)	141.4(1)
O(4)-Yb-O(8)	137.8(1)	O(8)-Yb-O(3a)	74.3(1)
O(4)-Yb-O(2a)	78.8(1)	Yb-O(1)-C(1)	147.2(3)
O(4)-Yb-O(3a)	122.3(1)	Yb-O(4)-C(8)	131.3(4)
O(5)-Yb-O(6)	71.7(1)	Yb(a)-O(2)-C(1)	141.6(3)
O(5)-Yb-O(7)	72.2(1)	Yb(a)-O(3)-C(8)	159.6(3)
O(5)-Yb-O(8)	123.8(1)		

 TABLE 3—ATOMIC COORDINATES ($\times 10^4$) AND ISOTROPIC THERMAL PARAMETERS ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$)^a

Atom	X	Y	Z	U_{eq}
Yb	1617(1)	121(1)	4119(1)	21(1)
N(1)	3111(4)	3937(4)	7572(3)	33(1)
N(2)	2259(5)	-1368(4)	7657(3)	34(2)
O(1)	2419(4)	1833(3)	5377(2)	39(1)
O(2)	674(4)	1834(3)	6180(2)	38(1)
O(3)	691(4)	-590(3)	6212(2)	37(1)
O(4)	2469(4)	-603(3)	5444(2)	35(1)
O(5)	2362(4)	-1646(3)	3673(2)	40(1)
O(6)	4552(4)	1037(3)	4437(3)	41(1)
O(7)	917(5)	-407(3)	2473(2)	44(2)
O(8)	2484(4)	2139(3)	3630(2)	37(1)
O(9)	3401(8)	3344(7)	1260(5)	98(3)
O(10)	4661(7)	2806(7)	2563(3)	90(3)
O(11)	4950(7)	2190(7)	1125(5)	92(3)
O(12)	2300(7)	1159(5)	1323(4)	84(3)
O(13)	6642(7)	2517(6)	9314(3)	76(3)
O(14)	6180(6)	2010(5)	7698(3)	70(2)
O(15)	8789(6)	2363(5)	8773(3)	65(2)
O(16)	8071(9)	4144(5)	8664(5)	100(3)
O(17)	8964(8)	4273(6)	6009(6)	110(3)
O(18)	8363(7)	5887(4)	5429(4)	75(2)
O(19)	7103(18)	3789(8)	4531(6)	194(7)
O(20)	6328(17)	4172(19)	5693(15)	259(13)
C(1)	2036(5)	2321(4)	6020(3)	30(2)
C(2)	3413(7)	3663(5)	6676(4)	43(2)
C(3)	2268(8)	4660(6)	7695(5)	56(3)
C(4)	1987(10)	4862(7)	8563(6)	75(4)
C(5)	2537(10)	4304(7)	9244(5)	70(3)
C(6)	3382(10)	3583(8)	9091(4)	68(3)
C(7)	3648(8)	3398(7)	8250(4)	56(3)
C(8)	1896(5)	-785(4)	6107(3)	31(2)

Table-3 (contd.)

C(9)	2849(8)	-1282(8)	6842(4)	59(3)
C(10)	927(7)	-2448(6)	7613(5)	61(3)
C(11)	383(10)	-2498(11)	8390(8)	106(6)
C(12)	1248(16)	-1467(16)	9175(7)	135(9)
C(13)	2580(16)	-397(13)	9198(5)	116(7)
C(14)	3086(10)	-356(7)	8434(5)	67(3)

^aThe isotropic parameters factor U_{eq} , is defined as one third of the trace of the orthogonalized U_{ij} tensor.

In this complex, the bond distances of Yb-O (carboxylato) and Yb-O (aqua) lie in the range 2.256(3)–2.325(4) and 2.337(3)–2.398(4) Å respectively, being different from those of a formal analogous compound Nd-pyBET², which has lightly longer Nd-O (carboxylato) 2.357(4)–2.440(5) Å and Nd-O(aqua) 2.457(4)–2.512(4) Å with average distances of 2.393(4) and 2.486(5) Å respectively.

Fig. 2. Molecular packing arrangement in the unit cell.

Those difference may be due to the lanthanoid contraction which make a fuller coordination of Yb, which has a smaller atom radius than that of Nd. As a result, Nd ion can only form a mononuclear complex and whose molecular structure is so loose that longer average Nd-O bond distance is obtained, meanwhile, the space groups are distinguished.

Conclusion : As neutral zwitterionic ligands, betaines have a strong tendency to form rare earth complexes, their crystal structures are affected by feature and structures of centre metal ions in a deep degree.

Experimental

The ligand pyridine betaine (pyridinioacetate, abbreviated to pyBET) was prepared according to the reported method³. ¹H nmr δ 5.28 (2H, s, CH₂), 8.11 (2H, t, *m*-H-py), 8.62 (1H, t, *p*-H-py), 8.83 (2H, d, *o*-H-py).

The title complex was prepared by mixing ytterbium perchlorate (A.R.; 0.6 g) with pyBET (0.275 g, 2 mmol) in warm water (5 cm³; 40°) with stirring. A colorless plate-like crystals were obtained and which were exposed for a week in air at room temperature (Found : C, 20.42; H,

2.54; N, 3.48; Yb, 21.30. Calcd. for : $[\text{Yb}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NCH}_2\text{-COO})_2 \cdot (4\text{H}_2\text{O})]_2 \cdot (\text{ClO}_4)_6$: C, 20.56; H, 2.71; N, 3.42; Yb, 21.16%. The density of the crystal was measured by floatation in $\text{CH}_2\text{I}_2/\text{CCl}_4$.

Ir spectra (KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, uv-reflectance spectra on a UV-240 spectrophotometer and epr spectra on a Varian X-E-4 spectrophotometer.

MoK_α ($\lambda = 0.71073\text{\AA}$) X-ray diffraction data (crystal class, orientation matrix, cell dimensions) were collected on an Nicolet R3m/E diffractometer in the $\theta/2\theta$ scan mode. Diffraction data were collected at 293 K (Table 1). To check reflections it was monitored every 120 measurement and no significant decay was observed. The data were corrected for Lorentz and polarization factors, and empirical absorption correction based on an ellipsoidal fit to Ψ -scan data was applied. The structure was solved by direct methods and refined by full-matrix least-factor techniques. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. Hydrogen atoms of pyridine betaine ligand were generated

in their idealized positions, assigned fixed isotropic temperature factors (0.08\AA^2), and included in the calculation of structure factors. All calculations were performed on a SDP-11/44 computer using the SHELEX 4.0 program package. Analytic expression of neutral atom scattering factors were employed, and anomalous dispersion correction were incorporated⁴. Final atomic coordination and equivalent isotropic temperature factors were collected.

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